

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

EVOLUTION OF ELECTRONIC GOVERNMENT IN THE REPUBLIC OF KAZAKHSTAN

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Abstract

The article considers the evolution of the process of formation and development of the model of the Electronic Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan based on digital technologies. Descriptions of stages of development of the Electronic Government are given. It is concluded that with the further strengthening of the digitalization process, the issues of cybersecurity and the need to transform the business processes of government agencies with integration with information systems of government agencies will be relevant.

Keywords: e-Government, digitalization, public services, mobile e-Government, quality of public services, interaction with the population.

In 2022, Kazakhstan took 28th place in the UN rating for the development of e-government. The country's government continues to systematically improve performance in this area.

In Kazakhstan, there is also a fairly valuable experience in developing the civil service, improving the work of civil servants with the public.

Based on successes and failures, a completely new concept was developed, which involved a revolutionary revision of the very philosophy of public service. For the first time, the term "public service" appeared, and the Government began to be perceived as a "service provider", and a citizen as a "service recipient". A fundamentally new model of functioning of government agencies based on digital technologies was being formed [1].

The economic and social effects, as well as the results of the implementation of the EP from 2005 to 2023, require fundamental research, since it is this case that can become one of the main components of the country's national brand.

So, in 2000-2005, the idea of creating an electronic government was initiated in the country through

the formation of digital interaction between the state and citizens as taxpayers.

The State program of formation and development of the national information infrastructure of the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2001-2005 was adopted for the development of telecommunications infrastructure, regulatory and methodological base of automation of the work of state agencies [2]. In the same period, the first Law "On Informatization" was adopted.

The process of digitalization of state activity began with the tax service in Kazakhstan. So, for the first time, operating rooms appeared in the tax services of the country, where taxpayers were served on the principle of "one window". The process of forming the e-government infrastructure has begun, tax committees have been modified, National Information Technologies JSC has been created.

Gradually, the philosophy of public service in Kazakhstan began to change towards the development and improvement of quality, the evolution of the model of public service in Kazakhstan based on digital technologies is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Evolution of the E-Government model in Kazakhstan

Note – compiled by the authors.

As can be seen from the figure, the path of formation of a modern model of Electronic Government (EP) with the provision of high-quality public services based on digital technologies in Kazakhstan took the period from 2005.

So, at the first stage in 2005-2008, the process of forming the e-government infrastructure began. Such projects as a unified transport environment, a national certification center, a server center, state databases of individuals, legal entities, real estate, addresses and others have been successfully implemented.

The domestic legislation was improved, where the concept of "electronic digital signature" (EDS) and "electronic document" was introduced. These were rev-

olutionary norms, thanks to which the status of an electronic document was for the first time equated to a paper document with a seal.

In 2006, the portal was launched egov.kz. In parallel, a program to reduce information inequality for 2007-2009 was launched. Free computer classes were opened to improve the digital literacy of the population – from children to pensioners, libraries and museum collections were digitized. In total, about 3 million people were trained.

After the creation of the basis, the second stage began – interactive. In Kazakhstan, at the first stage of the creation of egov.kz technologies "gateway of electronic government" will be introduced. This is the so-called "request router".

In 2008-2010, interactive services with the use of EDS were developed. People began to receive an address certificate, a criminal record certificate, register acts of civil status through the e-government portal, and also through special state bodies - PSC.

The emergence of PSC has changed government business processes. Quite a lot of business services have appeared, it has become possible to register companies and obtain licenses online, participate in online purchases and much more.

The third stage can be called transactional. More complex multicomponent services have appeared. A great achievement was the introduction of the "E-notary" and "E-licensing" systems.

Legislation on digitalization and EDS was developing, several types of electronic services were fixed, new institutions appeared that should be responsible for improving e-government. In particular, Zerde Holding received the status of the National Institute for the Development of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT).

Further on the egov portal.kz there are services involving the possibility of online payments. First of all, online payment of taxes, fees, duties and fines for traffic violations was implemented, in 2011 - payment for housing and communal services.

The fourth stage of e-government development is characterized by the "expansion of electronic public services", it was implemented within the framework of the state program "Information Kazakhstan 2013-2018". The active integration of information systems of government agencies began, more than 150 electronic services were implemented in total, infrastructure modernization was carried out, 4G standards were introduced.

The rapid growth of the number of Internet users has begun, the level of digital literacy has increased. More services appeared; e-commerce was actively developing. In particular, the procedure for applying for the conclusion of a marriage and registration of the birth of a child was completely automated, the basis for discussing draft laws and so on was opened.

The number of egov users.kz began to grow rapidly, the portal was already issuing 2-3 million certificates a year. There was a question of switching to a platform model. The Law "On Informatization" adopted in 2015 introduced the concept of an "information and communication platform of electronic government", the creation of which was to be started by JSC "NIT".

By order of the Minister of Information and Communications in 2018, the principle of platforming was approved, which provides for "the formation and continuous development of interdepartmental centralized technological platforms for the information and communication infrastructure of e-government and tools for solving common technical problems within various branches (spheres) of public administration." The principle of universality of solutions was also approved.

The next serious period, which can also be considered revolutionary, was the transfer of e-government to mobile technologies.

Even though egov.kz has been successfully operating since 2006 and provides online services for individuals and legal entities, citizens have increasingly switched to the use of mobile Internet and the use of smartphones in everyday life. Therefore, the development of a mobile EP was especially relevant.

Today, 678 public services are available in eGov Mobile, of which 204 are services and services of the egov portal.kz, 474 services for individuals of the e-license portal. About 2.4 million Kazakhstanis actively use it every month. About 50 thousand public services are provided here per month.

The Digital Documents service, popular among users, contains 20 documents. They can be used at the country's airports for domestic flights, when boarding cars at railway stations and buying tickets, at Otbasy Bank and UAPF branches and in other places.

The development of mobile EP contributed to the improvement of cybersecurity mechanisms. You can already log in to eGov Mobile using biometrics. Updates allow citizens to use more functionality. They are aimed at preserving the security of personal data.

In 2021-2023, a fundamentally new approach to the implementation of EP begins – this is the so-called "invisible government" and a proactive approach to the provision of electronic services. The new period will require a large-scale transformation of business processes, completion of the transition to the platform model and integration with the information systems of government agencies.

A serious challenge is the burden on the infrastructure due to the growing volume and complexity of data, as well as increased security requirements. Also, over the years since the launch of the infrastructure, technologies have evolved significantly. As a result, the relevance of the modernization of the existing e-government infrastructure has increased significantly.

Modernization of the unified transport environment of government agencies, construction of additional trunk communication channels, increasing the bandwidth of communication channels up to 100 Mbit/s, and in some points of the network – up to 10 Gbit/s are already relevant today. It is especially important to build new Server and Backup centers for storing government databases and systems of government agencies.

The risks of cyber threats and cyber-attacks are increasing, which requires updating both equipment and specialized software.

Thus, the case of the development of e-government in Kazakhstan shows that if there is political will, a competent team and motivation for the digital transformation of public administration, it is possible to achieve actual results and make a serious contribution to the development of the economy.

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